

GROWTH RATES IN AREA, PRODUCTION AND PRODUCTIVITY OF MAIZE IN MAHARASHTRA STATE

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Abstracts

The purpose of the present investigation was to study the district-wise compound growth rates in area, production and productivity of maize for the period of 40 years from 1980 – 81 to 2019–20 data were collected. For the overall state of Maharashtra, a very clear picture of changes in the area, production and productivity of maize can be seen. While at overall period under study, area, production and productivity of maize were positively significant at 8.24, 10.33 and 1.93 per cent, respectively. Among the study period, the III period was more satisfactory improvement in area production and productivity due to change in technology in all regions of Maharashtra. Thus, for the entire state, the increase in the production of maize was the combined effect of area expansion and productivity improvement in Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, Vidarbha regions and Maharashtra state as a whole

.Key words: Growth Rate, Area, Production and productivity

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays L.*) is one of the most versatile emerging crops having wider adaptability under varied agro-climatic conditions. It is cultivated on nearly 150 m ha in about 160 countries having wider diversity of soil, climate, biodiversity and management practices that contributes 36 per cent (782 mt) in the global grain production. The United States of America is the largest producer of maize contributes nearly 35 per cent of the total production in the world and maize is the driver of the US economy. The USA has highest productivity (> 11.13 t ha⁻¹) which is double than the global average (5.92 t ha⁻¹). Whereas, the average productivity in India is 3.24 t ha⁻¹. Maize is the third most important cereal crop in India after rice and wheat and is grown in a wide range of environments, extending from extreme semi-arid to sub-humid and humid region which predominantly occupies 82 per cent of the area under cultivation in the *kharif* season. Maize is the third most important cereal crop in India after rice and wheat and is grown in a wide range of environments, extending from extreme semi-arid to sub-humid and humid region which predominantly occupies 82 per cent of the area under cultivation in the *kharif* season. It accounts for around 10 per cent of total food grain production in the country. The Indian maize sector has several opportunities in all its sub- sectors like seed, non-seed inputs, farm mechanization, processed foods, industrial products, market-related infrastructure, storage, processing etc. Maharashtra was ranked 3rd in area under maize and rank 2nd under maize production among different maize producing states in the year 2020-21. Maize is grown in almost all the districts of all the region of Maharashtra.

Methodology

For the present study district wise yearly data of area, production and productivity of maize crop for the entire period (i.e., 1980-81 to 2019-20) were obtained from the Season and Crop Reports and Epitomes published by the Department of Agriculture, Maharashtra, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, GOI, ICRISAT and private institutions.

To facilitate proper understanding of percentage increase in area, production and productivity of maize, the period of 40 years from

1980 – 81 to 2019– 20 was divided into four sub periods and one entire period as indicated below.

1. Period I - 1980-81 to 1989-90
2. Period II - 1990-91 to 1999-2000
3. Period III - 2000-01 to 2009-10
4. Period IV - 2010-11 to 2019-20
5. Overall Period V - 1980-81 to 2019-20

Analytical Tools**Compound growth rates of area, production and productivity**

Compound growth rate were estimated to study the percentage increase or decrease in selected parameter. The following exponential growth function were used.

$$Y = ab^t e$$

$$\log Y = \log a + \log b + \text{error}$$

$$\ln(Y) = \ln(b_0) + bt$$

Where,

Y = Area, Production and Productivity

t = Time Period

b = regression coefficient

a = intercept

e = error term

$$\text{CGR (\%)} = (\text{Antilog } b - 1) \times 100$$

Results and Discussion

In the Western Maharashtra region, larger holdings and a greater proportion of cultivable lands led to the allocation of more land for maize, as evidenced by higher and significant growth in area by 4.64, 13.10, 14.17 and 5.54 percent, respectively, in the I, II, III, IV and overall period under study. The maize production significantly increased by 10.48 per cent, 23.60 per cent and 10.47 per cent, respectively, during periods II, III and overall, while production was non-significant in periods I and IV. The maize productivity has noticed positively significant by 8.26 and 1.62 per cent in period III and overall, but negatively non-significant in periods II and IV under the study. Thus, increased maize area and production in Western Maharashtra was primarily attributed productivity improvements.

Table 4.1.d Annual compound growth rate of area, production and productivity for maize in Maharashtra (1980-81 to 2019-20)

Particulars	Area	Production	Productivity
Western Maharashtra			
Period I	4.64 **	0.48 NS	-3.98 *
Period II	13.1 **	10.48 ***	-2.31 NS
Period III	14.17 ***	23.6 ***	8.26 **
Period IV	5.54 ***	1.76 NS	-3.58 NS
Overall Period	8.71 ***	10.47 ***	1.62 ***
R ²	0.9 ***	0.905 ***	0.311 ***

Marathwada			
Period I	9.6 ***	-2.33 NS	-10.88 ***
Period II	13.1 **	18.03 **	4.36 NS
Period III	6.2 ***	12.25 ***	5.7 *
Period IV	-4.27 NS	-10.72 *	-6.74 NS
Overall Period	8.56 ***	10.2 ***	1.51 ***
R ²	0.772 ***	0.058 NS	0.743 ***
Vidarbha			
Period I	6.61 *	1.5 NS	-4.8 NS
Period II	14.77 ***	18.05 **	2.85 NS
Period III	12.71 ***	22.28 ***	8.49 *
Period IV	1.3 NS	-2.2 NS	-3.45 NS
Overall Period	6.73 ***	8.66 ***	1.81 ***
R ²	0.348 *	0.09 NS	0.277 NS
Maharashtra			
Period I	6.22 ***	0.13 NS	-5.74 ***
Period II	9.25 ***	12.78 ***	3.24 *
Period III	10.91 ***	19.09 ***	7.37 **
Period IV	2.79 **	-1.05 NS	-3.74 NS
Overall Period	8.24 ***	10.33 ***	1.93 ***
R ²	0.806 ***	0.001 NS	0.686 ***

Note - *, ** and *** Significant at 10, 5 and 1 per cent level, respectively.

The table shows that there was a positively significant improvement in the area during periods I (9.60%), II (13.10%), III (6.20%) and overall (8.56%), but a negatively non-significant improvement during period IV (4.27%) in Marathwada region. In terms of production, positive and significant growth were observed in periods II (18.03%), III (12.25%) and overall (10.20%), whereas negative and non-significant growth was observed in periods I and negatively significant in period IV. Contrarily, the Marathwada region were noticed non-significant decline in productivity during period IV (6.74%) and during periods II (4.36%) was observed positively non-significant as well as a positive and significant increase during periods III and the overall study period of 5.7 and 1.51 per cent. In the Marathwada region, a clearer picture of maize production, area growth, and productivity could be seen.

In the case of Vidarbha, the significant growth in productivity by 8.49 per cent and 1.81 per cent in period III and overall period, respectively, and the significant expansion in area by 14.77, 12.71 and 6.73 per cent during period II, period III and overall period, respectively, were the causes of the significant increases in production of 18.05, 22.28, and 8.66 per cent during period II, period III and overall period. Whereas the productivity of maize were non-significant improvements of -4.8, 2.85, and -3.45 per cent were made during periods I, II, and IV, respectively. Thus, the area and productivity improvement has been impacted on maize production in the Vidarbha region.

For the entire state of Maharashtra, the same picture of changes in maize area, production and productivity can be seen. In period I, the area under maize had been increased significantly by 6.22 per cent, while production was non-significant (0.13%) and productivity was negative but non-significant (-5.74 per cent). In period II, there has been a positive improvement in the area, production and productivity by 9.25, 12.78 and 3.24 percent, respectively. Due to a significant increase in area by 10.91 per cent and a significant increase in productivity by 7.37 per cent in period III, there was a significant increase in production of 19.02 per cent. During period IV, the area was positively significant (2.79%), whereas production and productivity were negatively non-significant (1.05 and 3.74%), respectively. Therefore, for the entire state, the increased maize production was the combined effect of area expansion and productivity improvement.

Conclusion

It is clear from the above discussion above that area, production and productivity growth in Western Maharashtra were positively significant over the entire period (1980–2019) of study. It was suggested that, the increased maize production was the combined effect of area expansion and productivity improvement. However, the Marathwada, Vidarbha and Maharashtra states as a whole showed the same pattern positively significant change in area, production and productivity of maize, which indicated that the production of maize was increased due to area expansion and productivity improvement. Among the various periods, the fourth period's growth in area, production and productivity was non-satisfactory (2010-11 to 2019-20). It was mainly caused by erratic and irregular rainfall, dry spells and drought years between 2010–11 and 2017–18.

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